

THE IMPOLITENESS STRATEGIES IN PRESS CONFERENCE OF BOXING MATCH FOUND IN INTERNET

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ABSTRACT

The boxing match on 26 August 2017 was one of the biggest boxing match in the world. The match was held at T-Mobile Arena, Nevada America. The boxing matches faced the undefeated Boxing Champion Floyd Mayweather and the UFC Champion Conor McGregor. In boxing history, that was first time how the true champion of boxing faced the UFC champion. Floyd Mayweather is the real champion of boxing. He called himself as the 20-billion-dollar man. Floyd is known as the undefeated with perfect match record. Floyd defeated danger fighter from Mexico Juan Manuel Marquez and Filipino fighter Manny Pacquiao. Floyd's perfect match record during faced McGregor was 49 matched with 49 won and 27 KO. Floyd record in a Boxing match is 100% undefeated. In other side, as the challenger, the UFC champion Conor McGregor is also having good record. McGregor is a young talented UFC fighter. The called him as smart fighter. McGregor is an Irish professional martial art and professional boxer. His record is 24 matches with 21 won, 18 KO and get lost 3 times.

Introduction

The impossible has already happened. For the first time in boxing history, the boxing champion faced the UFC champion at boxing ring. The writer found the process to make this match happen is interesting. After his last fighting with Manny Pacquiao, Floyd said: he retired. McGregor always provoked Floyd to make him accepted his challenge. At least McGregor did more than one year to make him accept his challenge. McGregor always attached Floyd Mayweather.

The Press conference before the match is the biggest match between both of them. In press conference both of the fighters can attack in spoken, insult and provoke to each other. According to the writer the impoliteness used in press conference is interesting. The Press conference is one of way to promote the match. It was designed to make the match more interesting. Boxing is not only sport, it is not only fighting, more than that, this is about show on television. They made drama on boxing match. The place to make drama on stage is on press conference

before the match. There are many controversial things on press conference. Sometimes the fighter insult and fighting on press conference. The writer thinks it is interesting to investigate press conference Floyd and McGregor match because this is the match between the boxing champion and the UFC champion.

According to Culpeper (1996) impoliteness can be used to entertain people. To make controversy people did impoliteness. In boxing history, the greatest boxing legend Muhammad Ali was first boxer did impoliteness to make controversy. In that time, Muhammad Ali successfully made boxing match more interesting. What Muhammad Ali did is followed by the boxing generation after him. Controversy in boxing match will make the boxing match famous. The writer is interested to investigate impoliteness appeared in press conference of Boxing match Floyd Mayweather and McGregor because some reason. The first reason is because this match is facing the boxing champion and the UFC Champion. It never happened before in boxing history. The second reason, the writer found that this match happened because McGregor challenges Floyd first. To make Floyd accept his challenge, McGregor always provoked and insulted Floyd Mayweather on television. He ever said he can beat and knock down Floyd Mayweather. He did that until Floyd accepted his challenge. The writer investigated the press conference with impoliteness from Culpeper (1996). There were many studies of impoliteness for example. Murni and Solin (2012) investigated impoliteness

in title A Small Corpus Analysis on the Use of Impolite Language by Children. Cheng (2008) investigated impoliteness research in an intercultural apology. Mills (2008) made impoliteness research in cultural context. Mohammad (2013) made research in non-native speaker request. Garcia (2014) made research in debate. Biscetti (2015) made impoliteness research in title Impoliteness and Aggressiveness in Early Modern Master Servant Relations. Wicaksono (2015) made research in action movie. Those were impoliteness research made by some English students. What makes this research different is the writer makes research in Press Conference Boxing Match of Floyd Mayweather and McGregor. Press conference before boxing match is common to be done. What makes this press conference special is the fighter are not common. Floyd is the undefeated in boxing match and McGregor is the UFC Champion. First time in history how Boxing Champion in the world accepted the challenge from UFC Champion. The press conference of Floyd and McGregor was really hot. They ridicule and insult to make provocation. According to the writer the Press conference is interesting to be investigated with impoliteness theory.

Problem Statements

Based on the background of the study, the problems of the study will be formulated as follows:

- a. What kinds of impoliteness strategies were used by Floyd Mayweather in press conference?
- b. What kinds of impoliteness strategies were used by McGregor in press conference?

- c. What impoliteness strategies were mostly used by them to do face attack?

Objectives of the Study

The study aims at finding the answer to the question will state in the problem statement. Therefore, the objectives of the study are:

- a. To identify many kinds of politeness strategy used by Floyd Mayweather in press conference?
- b. To identify many kinds of impoliteness strategy used by McGregor in press conference?

1. Practical Benefits

In practically benefit of this research is as follows:

- a. For the writer
The writer can take lesson from this research.
 - b. For the readers
This research can enrich the reader knowledge of impoliteness.
- #### **2. Theoretical Benefits**
- a. This research will be enriching the research of impoliteness strategies.

Conclusion

The writer studied some impoliteness research conducted by some English students. The writer tried to find out something different in his research if his research is being compared with another research. The writer presents the previous of the study to prove the originality of this research. The previous studies are as follows. Mathias (2010) investigated a stylistic analysis of an extract from Dickens's *Great Expectations*.

- c. To identify most impoliteness strategies used by them to do face attack?

Limitation of the Study

This study will focus on impoliteness in press conference boxing match Floyd Mayweather and McGregor. Floyd Mayweather's impoliteness and McGregor impoliteness in press conference are taken as the data of this research.

Significance of the Study

This research will give some significant and contribution in teaching learning English both of theoretically and practically.

This research focuses on impoliteness incurred in a convivial setting of a Christmas dinner between lowborn people. As a result of the analysis of the text, target to establish another variety of impoliteness, namely "under-politeness" And also this impoliteness executed without rancor or anger which occasionally appears to be incidental and a result of socializing habits. Nevertheless, similar to other types of rudeness it creates feelings of discomfort, disharmony and even revenge. The analysis is made at the micro level of single utterances. Occasionally, more than one utterance is taken into consideration for the reconstruction of the speech activity to assist determining the exact degree of offense incurred. The method of analysis depends on positive and negative impoliteness strategies as proposed by Culpeper (1996, 2003). The aim of this paper support analysis of cooperation in the Christmas dinner in *Great Expectations*.

Murni and Solin (2012) analyzed Impolite Language Used by Children. They investigate Indonesian children Muslim writers producing impolite utterances through the characters and conflicts they create in the story books published by the Islamic publishers. This analysis focuses to find preliminary data on the impolite language used by children for further research, and at the same time showing how the data present children pragmatic incompetence and violation of the Quranic principles of being polite. And the findings of this analysis show that affective and coercive impoliteness presented in the stories. As well as this study finds the following: a) the issues which drive impolite utterances are competition between siblings, schoolmates, and bad teacher-student relationship; b) the lexicon used include animals, physical appearance, and behavioral assessment. In the level of syntax, declarative, interrogative, and imperative moods are used; c) the Quranic Principles violated by the impolite utterances are Quran Marufa (speaking nicely), Quran Karima (speaking honorably), and Quran Layyina (speaking softly); and d) the violation of the Quranic

principles is seen as reflecting the pragmatic incompetence of the characters and the authors in the way that they fail to create dialogues with refinement which reflect principles of Islam in the context of conflict.

Mills (2008) investigated impoliteness research in cultural context. In this research, she analyzes the way that generalizations about impoliteness at a cultural level are frequently underpinned by stereotypical and ideological knowledge. Both politeness theorists and more popular commentators on politeness often draw on emotionally charged views of other groups of people whom they characterize as not belonging to society, Statements about the growth of incivility and the decline of politeness are based on these ideological views. Mills agrees that these views of out groups and their levels of politeness are in part occasioned by the use of models of impoliteness which were developed to describe interaction at the level of the individual, rather than social models of politeness. She thinks we need to develop models of analysis which can more adequately capture changes which are taking place at the cultural level.

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